

Large Superficial Congenital Hemangioma: A Case Report

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Abstract

Vascular anomalies are of two types, vascular tumors, and vascular malformations. Infantile hemangiomas are benign vascular tumors found congenitally at birth or may develop later in infants. It is a messy mass made of blood vessels that are lined by endothelium. Congenital hemangiomas may be partly, completely, or non-involuting in nature. Such vascular tumors may start arising from fetal life and are presented in their full form at birth. Often vascular anomalies are associated with several types of somatic cell or germ cell mutations that may be found in the skin or mucosa of the body. One such case of large congenital capillary hemangiomas was found in the trunk region of a newborn infant; its various forms of presentations along with its developmental basis will be considered for the presentation.

Keywords: Benign, Congenital, Endothelium, Haemangioma, Tumour

Introduction

The vascular anomalies exist in the form of malformations in several fluid circulating channels in the body. They can attain various patterns, sizes, and they are seen on various locations mostly on the body surface, seldom they were seen as deep lesions inside the body. These channels involve the arteries, veins, capillaries, and lymphatic channels. The first 10 weeks of the gestation period are considered critical from the point of vasculogenesis. Haemangioblasts are the fundamental biological entities that play a role in de novo vascular channel formations¹. Vascular anomalies encompass the various types of anomalous presentations which may exist as an independent clinical presentation or it may be a part of various syndromes². Pathogenesis of hemangioma is multifactorial; such vascular malformation prevalence ranges from 0.3-1.5% worldwide³. Infantile hemangioma in newborn infants is most often a benign type. Clinical follow-up case studies have cited the incidence of superficial infantile hemangioma more frequently presented in the region of head and neck, but deeply seated hemangiomas were recorded with the lowest incidence rate. Presentation of large hemangioma in infants in the trunk region is relatively less common. One such rare infantile hemangioma and its various aspects will be considered in this article⁴.

Case report

Photo: 1 Showing Hemangioma

A newborn male infant was found with a pulsatile bluish brown mass showing tortuous vascular engorgements on its surface located behind the midaxillary line was found to be attached to the skin in the region of thoracic wall. Other than this baby was not found with any other anomalous features. Baby was shown to a pediatrician, no treatment or surgical interventions were advised and it was diagnosed as congenital vascular anomaly “**Hemangioma.**” In a span of 14 months the whole mass was gradually reduced by leaving a small scar on the body wall.

Ethical Clearance: Approved from the institutional ethical committee “JSSMC/IEC/18122023/23NCT/2023-24”

Discussion

Congenital hemangiomas are type of benign vascular tumors formed by hyperplasia of endothelial cells which are rapidly involuting most of which involute during post birth period. Vascular malformation is a spectrum of vascular morphological defect. Among them arteriovenous malformation (AVM) is at greater risk from the point of high blood flow with possibility of hemorrhage⁵. There are several benign vascular malformations, like capillary malformations, lymphatic malformations, venous malformations, arteriovenous malformations, etc. Capillary malformations are subtle vascular tumours probably involving

GNAQ mutations. Lymphatic canal anomalies may arise during the fetal life itself. Venous malformation manifested with vascular morphogenesis presented with vessel wall dilation, and flow stagnation with lesion expansion. It may involve endothelial receptor *TIE2* mutation of somatic cells. Arteriovenous malformations occur due to errors in vasculogenesis during fetal life where there is a direct shunting between the arterial and venous circulation in the absence of capillary bed formation. Haemangiomas are microscopically found with endothelium-lined blood spaces separated by septa⁶. Vasculogenesis involves the formation of Haemangioblasts cells, and angioblast cell proliferations which give rise to endothelial cells, followed by the formation of capillary scaffolding to form the primitive blood vasculature. Angiogenesis is a tightly regulated process involved in various physiological events like wound healing, menstruation, etc. There will be a physiological limit which is balancing between duration and intensity of pro-angiogenesis factors v/s anti-angiogenesis factors to drive such events⁷.

Vascular anomalies having their genetic origin involving the germ or somatic cells; the molecular influences will control the vascular morphogenesis. Based on the penetrance of genetic and molecular events, the vascular perturbations take a let-off for some duration; hence phenotypic presentation of some vascular anomalies may not be seen apparently in the initial period of life. The genetic signaling pathways like *RAS/MAPK* and *PI3K/AKT/mTOR* play a crucial role along with *TGF- β* signaling which play role in various vascular morphogenesis. Arteriovenous malformations (AVM) form a direct shunt between the arteries and veins by avoiding the capillary network. Which involves the *RAS/MAPK* pathway and *RASA1* mutations in AVM malformations⁸.

Though most of the infantile haemangiomas are having the tendency of spontaneous regression. However, the pathogenesis of infantile haemangioma is showing no clear consensus. Many experimental observational studies have underlain the molecular basis of IH. Haemangioma is a vascular tumor, that involves the proliferation of endothelial cells. These cells might get perturbations to form a vascular mass in situ or these cells might have migrated from a distant source like bone marrow. The haemangioma formation may include the event of vasculogenesis which is a de novo synthesis of blood vessels, or angiogenesis which is an augmentation of vasculature stem cells forming a tuft resembling a vascular mass. Such cells with the potency for intense proliferation which may eccentrically drive through potentially programmed haemangioma stem cells, later is originated from mesenchymal embryonic cells. This process is probably supported by the associated pericytes and several growth factors like VEGF which act as pro-angiogenesis markers which is a prime component that may be influencing both the

processes like vasculogenesis and angiogenesis which may be clinically presented with various form of vascular anomalies⁹. Large spectrum of vascular tumours needs keen clinical and diagnostic evaluation. The use of radio diagnostics needs a precaution, the ultrasound would be the safe measure for the clinical evaluation of extent of lesion. CT scan exposure should be avoided especially in infants; MRI would be ideal for the differential diagnosis and to study the lesion extension, in case if it is deeply seated in the musculoskeletal tissues to ascertain the diagnosis¹⁰. Optimum saturation of O₂ is critical for the cellular homeostasis. This event is driven through hypoxia-inducible-factor-1 (HIF-1) is an important transcriptional factor involved in hypoxic events to bring oxygen homeostasis by influencing the production of erythropoietin. HIF-1 plays an important role in angiogenesis; depleted oxygen content, tissue damage, infarction, etc. will influence or set the process of angiogenesis. HIF-1 can influence several genes of endothelial cells in the vessels. Indeed, the hypoxic state will play an important role since the early gestation period, it is a key factor inducing vasculogenesis followed by the development of a primitive heart. The probability of such a hypoxic situation during the early embryonic period might lead to prone locality of the body surface which might have led to the formation such vascular tumours¹¹.

Conclusions

The superficial infantile capillary hemangioma is a vascular tumor; often seen in specific locations on the exposed body parts; it is of keen cosmetic concern. Such congenital vascular lesions for the nuanced attention of vascular surgeons from the point of strategic clinical evaluation. Such congenital defects involve sporadic gene mutations in various types of cells. The present case is a gross expression of one such vascular tumor noticed at birth, understanding its anatomical, pathophysiological, and its molecular basis of such anatomical disarray will help in clinical diagnosis, and therapeutic standpoint.

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